

ONE OF THE IMPORTANT SKILLS IS VOCABULARY.

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Annotation: The article under discussion depicts applying the effective ways in improving vocabulary skills through interactive activities, exactly in learning the English language. The author of the article suggests several techniques to improve vocabulary acquisition.

Key words: vocabulary, communication, skills, verbally, learning, comprehend, essential, technique, improve.

When it comes to teaching English vocabulary, nothing beats the grammatical translation technique, which dates back to the 1500s. There are two approaches: reciting grammatical rules and translating sentences. Teaching English vocabulary comes second to reading classical literature when the goal is to learn vocabulary. Listening and speaking do not help to solidify the language that is read aloud in class. Flouting has been the direct technique since the late 1800s. The direct approach requires that each phrase be listened to and the student's handwriting reviewed afterward. In light of the shortcomings of the direct approach, several British and American academics started to adopt more contemporary strategies for learning languages. A word frequency and idiom table survey were used to rewrite the text and enhance foreign language teaching quality. After Globe War II, the United States improved how it teaches foreign languages to prepare its troops better to fight in various conflicts across the world. Used structural linguistics and behaviorist psychology used structural linguistics and behaviorist psychology to create the listening-talking technique. A system of rules controls language, according to structural linguists .

Most of us have not spent much time learning new vocabulary since we were high school or college students. Thankfully you can always pick up where you left off. Here are some tips to help you start learning new vocabulary words:

Develop a reading habit. Vocabulary building is easiest when you encounter words in context. Seeing words appear in a novel or a newspaper article can be far more helpful than seeing them appear on vocabulary lists. Not only do you gain exposure to unfamiliar words; you also see how they're used.

2. Use the dictionary and thesaurus. Online dictionaries and thesauruses are helpful resources if used properly. They can jog your memory about synonyms that would actually be better words in the context of what you're writing. A full dictionary definition can also educate you about antonyms, root words, and related words, which is another way to learn vocabulary.

3. Play word games. Classic games like Scrabble and Boggle can function as a fun way to expand your English vocabulary. Crossword puzzles can as well. If you really want to be efficient, follow up rounds of these word games with a little note-taking. Keep a list of the different words you learned while playing the game, and then study that list from time to time.

4. Use flashcards. A quick way to build a large vocabulary is to study a number of words via flashcards. In today's digital age, a wide array of smartphone apps make flashcards convenient and easy to organize. Aiming for one new word a day is reasonable. You can always go for more, but it may not be reasonable to assimilate dozens of English words every single day.

5. Subscribe to "word of the day" feeds. Some web platforms will provide you with a word a day—either on a website, an app, or via email—to help you expand your vocabulary. You can add these words to running word lists.

6. Use mnemonics. A mnemonic device is a form of word association that helps you remember words' definitions and proper uses. For instance think of the word obsequious which means "attempting to win favor from influential people by flattery." Break down that word into components: "obse" is the beginning of

“obsessed,” “oui” sounds like the French word for “yes” (oui), and “us” is like the word “us.” So you can think of that big word obsequious as “obsessed with saying yes to us”—which is kind of what it means!

7. Practice using new words in conversation. It’s possible to amass a huge vocabulary without actually knowing how to use words. This means you have to take it upon yourself to put your personal dictionary into use. If you come across an interesting word in your reading, make a point of using it in conversation. By experimenting in low-stakes situations, you can practice the art of word choice and, with a little bit of trial and error, hone in on the right word for a particular context. English is the official language of many countries around the world, and the way vocabulary is taught is constantly changing.

8. Create groups of words

As you learn new words, you can group them together by meaning. By creating these groups, you can identify patterns that make it easier to incorporate the words into your daily speech. For example, you might learn words like affirmative, efficacious and decisive, which all mean positive. By grouping these words together, it becomes easier to recall their general meanings and how to use them in speech.

9. Diversify what you read

Most people spend at least some of their time reading every day. Diversifying your reading choices can help you build a stronger vocabulary since you see new words from different writers who have varying writing patterns. Adding new texts and options to your reading list can also help.

10. Edit what you write

When you finish writing any professional text, such as an email or cover letter, review your content for repetitive words or phrases. Consider using your expanded vocabulary to replace words you used frequently throughout the document. By editing your own writing, you can improve clarity, style and tone.

The implementation of this strategy is efficient in terms of student learning. vocabulary accumulation. Like the bricks that make up a house, vocabulary is the

foundation and most important element of teaching English. If students have extensive vocabulary storage, it will be very helpful for English education in general. As a result, the authors of this paper believe that this essay will offer useful answers to the longstanding problem of teaching language effectively and efficiently. Since teaching vocabulary is a creative endeavor, educators can design their unique methods or techniques for teaching vocabulary based on their current situation and abilities.

You need good communication skills to work effectively with others in person, through email or by other means. Knowing which words to use and when is an important part of being a strong communicator. Building your vocabulary is one easy way to improve your communication skills. Having a large vocabulary can help you choose the right word or phrase needed for the situation, allowing you to easily convey your ideas, concerns, decisions and more.

Used literature:

1. Qodirberganovna, A. N. РОЛЬ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ И СТУДЕНТОВ В КОММУНИКАТИВНОМ МЕТОДЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЯЗЫКА В КЛАССЕ THE ROLE OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSROOM. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на*, 45.
2. Adamboeva, N. (2023). ASPECTS OF AXIOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS. *Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA»*, (March 10, 2023; Valencia, Spain), 163-166.
3. Qodirberganovna, A. N. (2023). Representation of Maximums in Axiolinguistic Evaluation of Politeness Category in Uzbek and English Languages. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(6), 39-41.

4. Adamboeva, N. (2023). XUSHMUOMALALIK KATEGORIYASINI AKSIOLINGVISTIK JIHATDAN TASNIFLASH NAZARIYASI. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(7).
5. Mirzayeva, G. S. (2022). Realiyaning Nutqimizdagi Milliy Va Madaniy Koloritini Ifodalashdagi O‘rni. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 30, 349-351.
6. Shohsanam, S. K. (2023). O‘QITUVCHI MULOQOT XULQINING ICHKI FUNKSIONALLASHUVIDA OVOZNING O‘RNI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(6 Part 6), 177-179.
7. Kakharova, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE TEACHER’S SPEECH IN THE CLASSROOM. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 1(6 Part 6), 173-176. Султанова, С. Р. (2023). ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПЕЙЗАЖНЫХ ОПИСАНИЙ В СТРУКТУРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(7), 987-992.
8. Султанова, С. (2023). СВОЕОБРАЗИЕ ЖЕНСКОГО ХАРАКТЕРА В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ РУССКИХ И АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПИСАТЕЛЬНИЦ В СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНОМ РАКУРСЕ. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(11).
9. Султанова, С. Р., & Давлятова, Г. Н. (2023). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВАРИАТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ РИТОРИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ. "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
10. Sultanova, S. R., & Nematov, S. X. (2023). FEATURES OF TURGENEV HEROINES IN THE APPEARANCE OF A MODERN GIRL. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(16), 113-117.
11. Sevara, S., & Timur, A. (2021). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. *Chief Editor*.

12. Sultanova, S., & Akhmadzhonov, M. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE «LITTLE MAN» IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19 CENTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 52-54.
13. Sevara, S., & Nigina, B. (2022). Degrees of Comparison of Adjective Names in Russian and Uzbek Languages. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(10), 105-108.
14. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2023). Theoretical Aspect of "Synecdoche "As a Stylistic Figure. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 249-254.
15. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. Cultural Comparison of Uzbek and English Language Speech Styles.
16. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2021). THE BRIEF INVESTIGATION OF CONTEMPORARY SPEECH STYLES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1280-1283.
17. Vaslidin o'g'li, N. M. (2023). Main Categories of Command Speech Acts. *Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History*, 17, 85-87.
18. Дадахонова, З. (2023). ТЕСТИРОВАНИЕ КАК СПОСОБ КОНТРОЛЯ НА УРОКАХ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(10), 1970-1973.
19. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF THE SKILLS AND ABILITIES OF THE STUDENTS. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(10), 106-110.
20. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF STUDENTSKNOWLEDGE, ITS FUNCTIONS AND PRINCIPLES. *NIDERLAND" INTEGRATION, EVOLUTION, MODERNIZATION: WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION"*, 14(1).